

observed that in methanolic solutions, while the O.D. around $430\text{ m}\mu$ showed a sharp increase immediately on mixing, followed by a gradual decrease with time, the O.D. around $530\text{ m}\mu$ increased gradually. The latter indicates the gradual increase in the concentration of the disubstituted product. Since none of the compounds, viz., *n*-hexylamine, chloranil and the disubstituted product have absorption peaks around $430\text{ m}\mu$, the initial increase in O.D. at this region has therefore to be associated with the formation of an intermediate, which then undergoes further reactions leading to the formation of the disubstituted product.

In order to obtain reliable information on the nature and composition of the intermediate it is necessary to determine the experimental conditions where :

- (1) the substitution reaction would not take place, or would be as slow as possible,
- (2) the O.D. around $430\text{ m}\mu$ ought to be measurable, and
- (3) the O.D. must not change with time, or changes so slowly that it can be measured reliably.

The O.D. measurements at $354\text{ m}\mu$ were employed for the detection of the disubstituted product.

Investigations showed that the above requirements can be nearly met in methanolic solutions only when

- (i) the amine concentration is lower than that of chloranil, and
- (ii) Chloranil concentration is less than 10^{-3} M .

This was necessary to obtain O.D. in suitable range (values obtained under such conditions were in the range 0.1–0.6 around $430\text{ m}\mu$ using 3 cm. cells). A severe restriction was thus put on the range of chloranil concentration since it was not possible to prepare solutions stronger than 10^{-3} M in methanol because of low solubility. Even, under such conditions the O.D. had to be measured rapidly because it changed with time. However, the change was very slow and extrapolation to zero-time was found unnecessary.

Measurements on Carbon tetrachloride solution as a function of time, however, showed that the measured O.D. at any instant at any wave length was always equal to the calculated sum of the absorptions due to unreacted chloranil and the disubstituted compound formed. Obviously, no intermediate with appreciable life is involved in carbon tetrachloride solutions. This peculiarity will be discussed later.

Since, in the present case, the concentrations of both the components were of the same order, it was not possible to apply Benesi-Hilderbrand equation in its usual form to evaluate the composition and formation constant of the intermediate. Neither was it possible to use Job's method as the amine concentration could not be made more than that of chloranil without greatly enhancing the rate of substitution. The following method was, therefore, developed.

Consider the equilibrium,

If D_0 and l be the O.D. and the path length of the solution respectively then,

$$D_0 = l\{\epsilon_A[A] + \epsilon_B[B] + \epsilon_{AB}[AB]\} \quad \dots (2)$$

Where, ϵ_A , ϵ_B and ϵ_{AB} are the molar extinction coefficients of A , B and AB respectively, while $[A]$, $[B]$ and $[AB]$ are the respective equilibrium concentrations.

If a , b and x be the initial concentrations of A , B and equilibrium concentration of AB respectively, equation (2) can be rearranged to give :

$$D_0 = l\{\epsilon_A \cdot a + \epsilon_B b + (\epsilon_{AB} - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_B)x\}$$

or,

$$x = \frac{D_0 - l(\epsilon_A \cdot a + \epsilon_B \cdot b)}{\Delta \epsilon \cdot l} = \frac{D_c}{\Delta \epsilon} \quad \dots (3)$$

where,

$$D_c = \frac{D_0 - l(\epsilon_A \cdot a + \epsilon_B \cdot b)}{l}$$

and

$$\Delta \epsilon = \epsilon_{AB} - \epsilon_A - \epsilon_B.$$

The equilibrium constant K , for reaction (1) is given by

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-x)}$$

or,

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \left[\frac{1}{K} + (a+b) \right] - \frac{a \cdot b}{x} \\ &= Y - \frac{a \cdot b}{x} \end{aligned} \quad \dots (4)$$

where,

$$Y = \frac{1}{K} + (a+b).$$

Substituting the values of 'x' from equation (3) in equation (4), followed by rearrangement gives

$$\frac{a \cdot b}{D_c} = \frac{Y}{\Delta \epsilon} - \frac{D_c}{(\Delta \epsilon)^2} \quad \dots (5)$$

If $(a+b)$, i.e., the total concentrations of the two components in a series of solution is kept constant, then it follows from equation (5) that a plot of $(a \cdot b)/D_c$ vs. D_c should give a straight line if 1 : 1 complex is formed. From the values of the slope and intercept K and $\Delta \epsilon$, ϵ_{AB} can be calculated.

Representative spectrophotometric data on *n*-hexylaminechloranil system in methanol are given in Tables I and II. The plots of $(a \cdot b)/D_c$ vs. D_c are shown in Fig. 3. Reasonable linearity between $(a \cdot b)/D_c$ and D_c (Fig. 3) at different wave lengths clearly indicates the formation of 1 : 1 intermediate. Further, the values of Y (equation 5) which should be

same for plots at different wave lengths if 1 : 1 complex is formed, lie within a very narrow range (0.968×10^{-3} to 1.1012×10^{-3} at six different wave lengths). The average value of the equilibrium constant 'K', calculated from the average value of 'Y', is 2.84×10^4 .

TABLE I

Spectrophotometric data

Concentration of Chloranil (a) = $0.943 \times 10^{-3} M$
 ,, of n-hexylamine (b) = $0.943 \times 10^{-3} M$
 $a+b$ = $0.943 \times 10^{-3} M$
 $l = 3$ cms.

Sl. No.	Composition of Solution		O.D. at wave lengths shown (D_o)			
	Vol. of Chloranil in ml.	Vol. of amine in ml.	400m μ	420m μ	430m μ	440m μ
1.	10.0	0.0	0.375	0.190	0.136	0.096
2.	9.5	0.5	0.398	0.233	0.180	0.136
3.	9.0	1.0	0.422	0.277	0.224	0.184
4.	8.5	1.5	0.455	0.325	0.276	0.228
5.	8.0	2.0	0.480	0.351	0.312	0.260
6.	7.5	2.5	0.508	0.405	0.361	0.312
7.	6.0	4.0	0.545	0.490	0.445	0.397

TABLE II

Values of $\frac{a.b}{D_c}$ and D_c at various wave lengths.

Sl. No.	400 m μ		420 m μ		430 m μ		440 m μ	
	(1)*	(2)*	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
1.	0.042	113.1	0.052	91.4	0.051	93.1	0.045	105.5
2.	0.084	107.1	0.106	84.9	0.102	88.2	0.098	91.8
3.	0.136	93.7	0.163	78.2	0.160	79.7	0.146	87.3
4.	0.180	88.9	0.199	80.4	0.203	78.8	0.183	87.4
5.	0.227	82.6	0.262	71.6	0.259	72.4	0.240	78.1
6.	0.320	75.0	0.376	63.8	0.363	66.1	0.339	70.8
7.	0.367	68.1	0.430	58.1	0.417	60.0	—	—

* Column (1) gives the values of D_c and column (2) gives the values of $\frac{a.b}{D_c} \times 1.125 \times 10^8$

It is worthwhile to mention here that the possibility of the intermediate being the mono-substituted derivative due to an equilibrium of the type :

was ruled out since the test for chloride ion was always negative as long as no disubstituted product was formed.

Although the composition of the intermediate has been shown to be 1 : 1 nothing definite can be said about its structure. However, certain conjectures may be made on the basis of various observations. The inability to observe the intermediate formation in

carbon tetrachloride, as mentioned earlier, may be explained by assuming the dipolar structures I or II for the intermediate.

Such a structure would be stabilised in highly polar solvents like methanol and may exist for appreciable time, while in carbon tetrachloride, such an intermediate, if at all formed, will tend to undergo further reaction immediately, and may therefore, escape detection.

Although reversible addition to the carbonyl group of the quinones and substituted quinones is known to occur quite readily with hydroxy² and bisulphite³ groups, it has been shown that OH⁻ addition to chloranil follows very fast substitution of chloride at 2-position, probably through an intermediate similar to I². However, the intermediate I would be expected to be more stable than the corresponding intermediate involving OH⁻, as the displacement of the Cl⁻ in the latter may be enhanced due to the availability of lone pair electrons on the oxygen.

The structure I, therefore, seems most probable. Further work is in progress.

Sincere thanks are due to Professor Sadhan Basu, University of Calcutta, for helpful discussions.

Department of Chemistry,
University of North Bengal,
West Bengal.

Received July 12, 1968
Revised MSS received February 27, 1970

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Note added in the proof: E.S.r measurements on the present system recently carried out by us indicate the intermediate to be a para-magnetic species. The implications of the e.s.r data will be communicated in Part III.